

THERAPEUTIC AND ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF LOCAL PLANTS IN TEHSIL TANGI, DISTRICT CHARASADDA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The present study investigated ethnobotanically valuable plants of Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda, Pakistan. Data was collected from November 2023 to October 2024 from different localities in all four seasons of the year. A total of 84 plant species were collected, belonging to 51 families among which 41 (48%) species were herbs, 25 (29%) were trees, and 18 (21%) species were shrubs. Euphorbiaceae was the most dominant family with five species, followed by Moraceae and Asteraceae, each with four species – the families most frequently present in the study area. Among the collected plants used as resources, 41 (48.23%) were fuelwood species, 31 (37.64%) were fodder species, 21 (24.70%) were shelter plants, 7 (8.23%) were ornamental, 10 (8.50%) produced edible fruit, 16 (18.82%) were used as vegetables, and 9 (10.58%) had other uses. The medicinal plants were most commonly used to treat diarrhea (7; 8.23%), headache (2; 3.20%), toothache (4; 5.43%), as carminatives (8; 9.56%), cough and cold (6; 7.20%), fever (5; 6.15%), eye irritation (2; 3.20%), wounds (4; 5.43%), as tonics (7; 8.23%), diabetes (6; 7.20%), as blood purifiers (6; 7.20%), stomachache (3; 4.20%), dysentery (8; 9.42%), as laxatives (6; 7.20%), and as pain killers (5; 6.15%). People still use these medicinal recipes to cure diseases. These medicinal plants require proper conservation for future use.

Map of the Tehsil Tangi District Charsadda.

INTRODUCTIO

Tehsil Tangi (34°18'0"N 71°39'14"E), one of the three administrative units of District Charsadda in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, comprises 12 union councils, including the headquarters at Tangi. It lies approximately 17 miles northwest of Peshawar, with a population that increased from 254,461 in 1998 to 428,239 in 2017 (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2017). The soils of Tangi are primarily loamy, sandy loamy, and clayey, while exposed rocky surfaces have gravelly textures. The steep slopes are susceptible to erosion, and moderate slopes have fertile soils that can be put to productive uses. The region is suitable to the cultivation of major crops like maize, wheat, rice and sugarcane and orchards with pomegranate, apricot, peach, walnut and grape. There is cultivation of vegetables like okra, tomato and beans both uncommercially and commercially. The Peshawar Plains, with an area of approximately 996 km², are fertile and good habitat in agricultural and ecological studies hence Tehsil Tangi is a significant area to study ethnobotanical. Ethnobotany is the branch of the science that focuses on the interactions between humans and plants and examines the utilization

of plants by humans in medicinal, nutritional, cultural, and economic applications (Mishra et al., 2025). Such interactions depend on the environmental conditions, traditions, and the availability of resources (Fisher et al., 2021). Ethnobotanical information is a significant basis of contemporary pharmacology because many bioactive pharmacologically active compounds have been discovered by using plants traditionally (Dean, 2024). The use of natural plants in the form of herbal medicines remains a major form of primary health care to almost 80 percent of the global population due to their efficacy, availability, cost and usually low side effects (Mukherjee et al., 2006). The use of medicinal plants dates back to ancient times and the treatment of numerous disorders, due to the abundance of bioactive substances and the variety of pharmacological activities (Dar et al., 2023). Plant based medicine is historically documented in Mesopotamia in 2600 BCE, when oils derived out of *Cedrus*, *Cupressus sempervirens*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Commiphora*, and *Papaver somniferum* are reported to have been used (Giannenas et al., 2020). Even though certain

ancient medicine was founded on superstition like the doctrine of signatures that proposed the form of a plant determined its medicinal qualities, the traditional medicine provided the foundation of modern drug discovery, and serves as an inspiration in the development of new drugs (Chaachouay and Zidane, 2024). The Unani system of traditional medicine is still practiced in large numbers in Pakistan, with over 50,000 registered hakims who use different parts of plants, leaves, roots, and barks, fruits, and seeds to treat diseases in humans and animals (Hassan et al., 2017). The rural communities are highly indigenous in their knowledge of medicinal plants, and usually, they make treatments through their traditional methods (senku et al., 2022). Nevertheless, these forms of traditional knowledge are mostly passed on through the word of mouth and face the threat of extinction because of urbanization and modernization (Arjona-Garccia et al., 2021 and Rahim et al., 2025). Thus, it is essential to preserve and record this ethnobotanical data so that it could be used by the future generations and scientific development. Pakistan boasts of nine major ecological zones and also has good climatic conditions, which support approximately 6,000 different plant species, out of which only approximately 600 have been scientifically reported to be utilized in terms of their medicinal benefits (Shinwari et al., 2003). Several works on ethnobotany have been done in various areas such as Margalla Hills National Park (Ali, 2008), Ayubia National Park (Shinwari and Gilani, 2003), Kahuta, Rawalpindi (Qureshi and Khan, 2001), Swat, and Chitral (Ali and Qaiser, 2009). These surveys also demonstrate the ethnomedicinal richness of Pakistan and underline the necessity to preserve the plant diversity.

In the currently understudy region, Tehsil Tangi, people rely on the primary healthcare given by medicinal plants. These commonly used species are *Fagoniacretica*, *Inula grantioides*, *Otostegialimbata*, *Tribulus terrestris* and *Asphodelus fistulosus* which is traditionally treated against blood purification and kidney disorders (Ahmad, 2005). However, much of this knowledge remains

undocumented. Hence, this study aims to record and analyze the ethnomedicinal knowledge of local communities in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda, to preserve indigenous practices and contribute to the understanding of Pakistan's valuable medicinal flora.

Methodology

To carry out the ethnobotanical study, research was undertaken to collect plant specimens, ethnobotanical information, and data on the medicinal uses of plants in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda. The study was conducted from November 2023 to October 2024. Several field trips were arranged to collect plant specimens, which were gathered with their roots and rhizomes. Ethnobotanical data were recorded together with the specimens. During fieldwork, questionnaires were used to interview local people to learn local names, medicinal uses, and other ethnobotanical uses of the plants. Data was collected from elderly expert informants. They were also asked how they used these plants (for example, green or dried, and singly or in combination with others). Repeated queries were made to confirm the information. The plants were dried, preserved, and mounted on standard herbarium sheets according to the procedures of Forman and Bridson (1989) and Ali (2011). These preserved plants were identified according to Ali & Nasir (1989–1991), Nasir & Ali (1970–1989), the Tropics Project of Pakistan, and other available literature.

Results and Discussion

A total of 84 ethnobotanically important plant species, representing 51 families, were recorded from Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda. The documented flora depicts ecological variability as well as the experience of the local people (Jan et al., 2021; Jan, Abbasi et al., 2013). Euphorbiaceae was the most prevalent family amongst the recorded with Moraceae, Asteraceae, Lamiaceae, and Zygophyllaceae taking the third, fourth, fifth and sixth positions respectively. The richness of these species of these families corresponds to the works of Swat, Buner, and Dir, in which such families as Euphorbiaceae and

Moraceae were often mentioned in relation to their ethnomedicinal significance (Khan, Shinwari, and Hussain, 2015; Ahmad, Khan, and Hussain, 2014). The most abundant life was herbs (41 species, 48%), trees (25 species, 29%) and shrubs (18 species, 21%). Herbs domination is in line with past ethnobotanical surveys in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, which document that herbs are used to prepare local remedies because their availability, quick regeneration, and preparation are easy (Asfaw et al., 2022; Shah and Hussain, 2012). *Acacia nilotica*, *Chenopodium album*, *Citrus medica*, and *Mentha arvensis* were used to treat diarrhea, dysentery, and abdominal pain (Abd El-Ghani, M. M., 2016). *Foeniculum vulgare*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Otostegialimbata*, and *Eucalyptus lanceolata* were used for cough, cold, asthma, and bronchial congestion (Nasrullah, Khan, & Shah, 2017). *Calotropis procera*, *Withaniasomnifera*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, and *Fagonia indica* were applied for cuts, wounds, burns, and skin infections (Adnan, Khan, & Shah, 2014). *Citrus aurantifolia*, *Olea ferruginea*, *Melia azedarach*, and *Zizyphus jujuba* were used traditionally to control blood sugar levels (Rehman, & Shah, 2018). Overall, medicinal plant use reflects a reliance on traditional healthcare systems, particularly in areas with limited access to modern medicine (Khan et al., 2015; Hussain et al., 2018). Leaves (40%) were the most preferred plant part used as indigenous medicine, followed by whole plants (31.76%), fruits (23.52%), stems (18.60%), seeds (7.37%), roots (6.37%), flowers (4.08%), and gums (3.2%) (Abbasi et al., 2013; Shinwari &

Qaiser, 2011). Several species, such as *Avena sativa*, *Chenopodium album*, *Morus alba*, *Dodonaeaviscosa*, and *Acacia modesta*, were used as fodder, fuelwood, and timber. This multifunctional use aligns with patterns reported in Charsadda and Swabi, highlighting the integral role of plant resources in rural livelihoods (Hussain et al., 2019; Alam & Abbasi, 2015). Plants serving as vegetables, fruits, and condiments included *Amaranthus viridis*, *Chenopodium album*, and *Nasturtium officinale* (vegetables); *Morus nigra*, *Zizyphus* spp., and *Diospyros kaki* (fruits); and *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha arvensis*, and *Cymbopogon citratus* (aromatic herbs). These uses correspond with findings in similar ethnobotanical surveys across Pakistan, where edible plants also serve medicinal roles (Badshah & Hussain, 2011). *Peganum harmala* was used in spiritual and cultural practices, a pattern widely reported in South Asia (Shah & Hussain, 2012). Several economically and medicinally important species (*Withaniasomnifera*, *Calotropis procera*, *Fagonia indica*, *Dodonaeaviscosa*, *Morus alba*) face overharvesting, habitat loss, and unsustainable grazing pressures. Similar threats have been highlighted in previous studies from Pakistan (Shinwari & Qaiser, 2011; Hussain et al., 2019).

Table 1. List of plant species showing their botanical name, family, local (vernacular) name, parts used, and ethnobotanical uses

S. No.	Plant Name	Family Name	Local Name	Part used	Ethnobotanical uses
1.	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Delile.	Mimosaceae	Kikar	Stem leaves	The stem and root decoction locally used for the treatment of dysentery and diarrhea
2.	<i>Acacia modesta</i> Wall	Mimosaceae	Palosa	Wood gum flower stem	Wood is used as fuel, and the leaves serve as fodder. The gum is used as a tonic and to treat dysentery and weakness. A decoction of the bark is taken for abdominal pain, while gum mixed with milk is used to relieve backache.
3.	<i>Agaricus campestris</i> L.	Agaracaceae	Kharey	Whole body	Cooked as food
4.	<i>Allium cepa</i>	Liliaceae	Piaz	Fruit	Should down the heart beat fats.
5.	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Ghanhar	Leaves	Leaves are used as vegetable. also used as fodder for animal food. The dry plant also used for feul.
6.	<i>Aconitum Violaceum</i>	Ranunculaceae	Zahar mora	Roots	it is used as antidote, anti-inflammatory and snake bites, also used as infections in intestine.
7.	<i>Adiantum capillus</i> L.	Adiantaceae	Sumble	Leaves, stem	Leaf used as decoction. Used for cough and fever.
8	<i>Avena sativa</i> L.	Poaceae	Jawdar	Whole plant	Spikes are used as nerve tonic, laxative and antiseptic. The plant is also used as fodder.
9	<i>Acyranthus aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Unknown	Roots	Roots are used for stomach, urine formation and cough.
10	<i>Albizia lebback</i>	Papilionaceae	Sreekh	Whole plant	Whole plant used as a fuel and sheltering.it also used for furniture making. It is also honeybee's specie.
11	<i>Anagallis Arvensis</i> L.	Primulaceae	Mangoty	Leaves	Used as vegetable (saag)
12	<i>Brassica compistrus</i> A.	Brassicaceae	Sharsham	Whole plant	Oil is extracted from seed which is used for cooking. The plant is used as a fodder. It also honeys bee's species.
13	<i>Broussonetia papyrefira</i>	Moraceae	Gultooth	Whole plant	Also used for feul. The wood is used for ice-cream making chamber, and leaves are used as fodder.
14	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	Fabaceae	Kachnar	Leaves, bark and flower	Leaves and flower analgesic, cough, tonic, diarrhea. Bark toothache.
15	<i>Callistemon lance latus</i>	Myrataceae	Brush booty	Whole plant	It is also cultivated for ornamental purposes and also used for fuel.
16	<i>Conyza Canadensis</i> L.	Composite	Maloch booty	Leaves	Its leaves are boil in green tea and used for the

					treatment of diarrhea.
17	<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	Chenopodaceae	Sarmy	Whole plant	The plant is commonly used as a vegetable and has sweet, digestive, and laxative properties. It is used to treat peptic ulcers, cardiac, and spleen disorders, while the roots are used for jaundice and urinary diseases
18	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> W.	Convolvulaceae	Prewathy	Leaves and shoot	Commonly used as fodder and as <i>saag</i> . It is given to children to expel intestinal worms and is also used to treat skin disorders; plant extract is applied for skin diseases
19	<i>Citrus medica</i> L	Rutaceae	Narang	Fruit and leaves	Bark is used as feul. Green leaves are used for making tea which is used to prevent vomiting. It also relives constipation, prevent dehydration.
20	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Poaceae	Kabal	Whole plant	The plant is used to treat thirst, biliousness, vomiting, fever, dysentery, blood disorders, and skin diseases including leprosy and scabies. Plant juice is used for hysteria and epilepsy, while the decoction serves as a blood purifier and diuretic.
21	<i>Citrus aurintifolia</i>	Rotaceae	Nambo	Fruit and leaves	Anti-diabetes, anti-hypertensive, protect heart, liver bone and prevent urinary disease. Use in jams, pickles and jellies.
22	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Graminaceae	Lemon grass	Leaves	used for the treatment of fever, stomachs problems, diabetes disease.
23	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Asclapedaceae	Spalmy	Whole plant	The dried plant is used for feul. The ash is used for the colour of cloth. The dried leaves were granded into powder, thin mixed with ghur and its paste used for snake bite. latex aris used ringworm and skin disease.
24	<i>Cyprus rotundus</i>	Cyperaceae	Della	Whole plant	The plant is used as fodder for animal.
25	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>	Cuscutaceae	Shatara	Leaves and stem	Stem is used for fever and skin itching, also used as antifertility agent.
26	<i>Capsella bursa</i>	Brassicaceae	Unknown	Leaves	Leaves and flowering tops are cooked as vegetables, used as salad, and also serve as fodder for cattle.
27	<i>Coronopus didymus</i>	Brassicaceae	Skhaboty	Whole plant	Blood purifier, help in digestion.

28	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Canabinaceae	Bhang	Leaves	Flower and leaves are used to obtain hashish which is a narcotic drug used in headaches.it is used for asthma and dysentery.
29	<i>Chrozophora tinctoria</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Unknown	Leaves	Used for the treatment of fever and emetic.
30	<i>Dysphonia ambrosides</i>	Amaranthaceae	Unknown	Leaves	It used as a purgative, analgesic and vermifuge to expel round worms and hook worms.
31	<i>Diospyrus kaki</i>	Ebenaceae	Sor amlok	Fruit, leaves and stem	Fruit is edible and also source of income for the local's area. Leaves are used as fodder for cattle, also used for foul.
32	<i>Doucus carota</i>	Apiaceae	Gajar	Fruit	The plant is used as fodder. Also useful for heart vessels weakness. Important source for vitamins.The juice of carrots when taken with almond provide brain strength.
33	<i>Dodonea viscosa</i>	Sapandaceae	Dodoneaviscosa	Whole plant	branch is used in construction for roofs. The plant is collected, dried and used as feul. The plant used as anthelmintic. Leaves of the plant act as stimulant. Decoctions of plants are used in swelling and wound.
34	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	Solanaceae	Bathura	Seed and leaves	Seed and leaves are both poisonous. Leaves are applied on boil for maturation.
35	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Mandaro	Whole plant	Plant is used for feul. Latex is poisonous and causes swelling on skin also causes irritation.
36	<i>Euphorbia prostrate</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Zeelay	Leaves	Sun burns.
37	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Sezonky	Seed	Seeds are used as tonic and for the treatment of diarrhea.
38	<i>Eucalyptus lanceolate.</i>	Myrataceae	Lachi	Whole plant	Stem and branches are used for shelter and burning purposes as well as for furniture. The dried branches of the plant are used as fuel. Leaf decoction is used as antipyretic, carminative, expectorant and antiseptic.
39	<i>Eugenia jamblana</i>	Myrataceae	Jaman	Fruit, stem and leaves	The fruit is edible and used for liver disorders. Bark is used as a mouthwash, seeds for diabetes, and leaves to treat dysentery.
40	<i>Equisetum arvensis</i>	Equisetaceae	Bandaky	Whole plant	Used for inflammation of urinary bladder and other urine problems.
41	<i>Foeniculum vulgar</i>	Apiaceae	Kaga	Fruit	Fruit is used as carminative, used to control vomiting, and as flavoring agent.

42	<i>Ficus carica</i> ⁶	Moraceae	Inzar	Fruit stem latex leaves and wood	Fruit is edible and used for shelter as well as fuel. Bark is used for fuel. Leaves used as fodder. It is used as expectorant, laxative, anti-constipation, correct piles and urinary bladder problems.
43	<i>Fagonia indica</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Azghaky	Whole plant	The dried plant is used as fuel. The whole plant, and extracts from its stem and leaves, are used as a blood purifier and to treat skin diseases.
44	<i>Jaglan regia</i>	Juglandaceae	Ghuz	Fruit, bark and leaves	The fruit is edible and consumed as a dry fruit. Peel, bark, and roots (locally called <i>danda</i>) are used for cleaning teeth and coloring lips.
45	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	Meliaceae	Tora shandy	Whole plant	Leaves are used as anti-diabetics. Wood is used for furniture. Used for flatulence in animal, leaves and grain used as insecticide's
46	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	Labiaceae	Podina	leaves	Used for the discharge of sputum in the lungs, heart problems and for the family planning
47	<i>Morus nigra</i>	Moraceae	Tor tooth	Fruit leaves and wood	Fruit is edible. Wood is used in making furniture and fuel. Leaves used as fodder for cattle.
48	<i>Morus alba</i>	Moraceae	Spin tooth	Fruit leaves and wood	Fruit is edible. Wood is used in making furniture and fuel. Leaves used as fodder for cattle.
49	<i>Malvastrum coromandelianum</i>	Malvaceae	Unknown	Whole plant	The dry plant is also used for fuel. Cooling emollient inflamed sores resolving, decoction in dysentery
50	<i>Monothecea buxifolia</i>	Sapotaceae	Gurgura	Stem and fruit	The stem of plant is used as shelter and fuel. The fruit is used as food. The plant is grazed by grazing animals. The leaves and flowering stem used as antiasthmatic antispasmodic and carminative
51	<i>Medicago denticulate</i>	Papilionaceae	Peshtary	Leaves	Whole plant is used as diuretic, also used in jaundice.
52	<i>Melilotus indicus</i>	Fabaceae	Lewany	Seed	Used as diarrhea, emollient, astringent and used for swelling. Also used as vegetable.
53	<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	Lamiaceae	Venally	Leaves	Leaves are used to reduce gastric acidity used as carminative and relieve abdominal pain. leaves are widely used to flavor locally used in (chatni).
54	<i>Nasturtium officinal</i>	Brassicaceae	Tarmera	Leaves	Cooked as vegetable.
55	<i>Nerium olender</i>	Apocynaceae	Ghandary	Whole plant.	The dried plant is used as fuel and for ornamental purposes. Dried, ground leaves are used to manage

					diabetes. A paste of dried roots is applied to treat skin diseases, snakebite, and scorpion stings. Leaf decoction is used to reduce swelling.
56	<i>oxalis corniculata</i>	Oxalidaceae	Trewakay	Whole plant	Eaten fresh and use as spice. used as perfect remedy for jaundice.
57	<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	Oleaceae	Zetoon		Olive oil is used externally as antiseptic and anodyne. leaves are used in diabetes. Wood is used as fuel.
58	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	Lamiaceae	Kashmaly	Leaves and Seed	Leaves are used in cough and flu. Seeds are added to cold drinks. also grown as ornamental.
59	<i>Otostegia limbata</i>	Lamiaceae	Spin azghay	Whole plant	Leaves are browsed by goats and sheep and used as fodder. The plant is used for washing utensils, as fuel, for hedges, and for shelter. Dried plants serve as firewood. Leaf paste treats sore throats, while boiled leaf extract and young leaves are used for mouth ulcers and skin diseases.
60	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Piperaceae	Tor mirch	Fruit	The fruits are laxative, carminative and purgative It also used as anti-oxidants.
61	<i>Peganum harmilla</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Spalanay	Whole plant	The plant is grazed by grazing animals. The plant is collected, dried & used for evil explosion. Dried seeds are used against antibacterial. It gives pleasant smell & fruit is used for gas trouble.
62	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	Asteraceae	Jarro booty	Roots	Roots are first boiled in water and then crushed, and extraction is thin used for the treatment of dysentery.
63	<i>Platanus orientalis</i>	Platanaceae	Chinar	Leaves and wood	Leaves are used in dysentery. Wood is used for making furniture, timber, and also as fuel.
64	<i>Rosa webbiana</i>	Rosaceae	Zangalli Gulab	Whole plant	It's used for making hedges and ornamental. It is also used for sheltering purposes.
65	<i>Rumex dantatus</i>	Polygonaceae	Shalkhay	Whole plant	Mostly cooked as vegetable. it is astringent and is used in skin disease. Also used to treat constipation in cattle.
66	<i>Rosa damascene</i>	Rosaceae	Sur gullay	Flower	Flower is used as sedative.
67	<i>Rosa indica</i>	Rosaceae	Gulab	Flower	Stomach problems and eye diseases.
68	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Arunda	Seed	Dried plants are used as fuel. Extremely used for wound healing & seeds make animals sterile. Grinded seed paste is used for animal constipation. Seed oil is used

					for snake bite
69	<i>Salix alba</i>	Salicaceae	Kharwalla	Wood and leaves	Leaves are used externally as warming agents to relieve pain. Wood is used for furniture and timber, also used as feul.
70	<i>Solanum surrattanse</i>	Solanaceae	Maraghoni	Seed	Used as fuel. Used for hedge purposes. Extract is used for epilepsy & hysteria. Fruits are used for constipation, sore throat and purgative. Leaves extract is used as rheumatism. Decoction of stem, flowers and leaves is used as carminative. Leaves are used for treatment of teeth pain.
71	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica L.</i>	Loganiaceae	Lalshora	Fruit and wood	Aphrodisiac, stimulant, tonic, digestive problems.
72	<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	Chenopodaceae	Palak	Leaves	Used for the treatment of skin disease and removal of body poisons. Used for the deficiency of blood and dysfunction of brain may be taken 25 to 50 gram.Used as fodder.
73.	<i>Salvia moorcroftiana</i>	Labiata	Kharghwag	Rhizome and leaves	Rhizome powder mixed with crushed <i>Vitex</i> leaves is given to buffaloes for colic. Crushed leaves mixed with wheat flour are fed to increase milk production.
74	<i>Sonachus asper</i>	Asteraceae	Shodapai	Whole plant	Mostly used as fodder and believed to increase milk production. Latex from young plants is alkaline and used to stain clothes
75	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i>	Aizoaceae	Inset	Leaves	The leaves of the plant cooked as vegetable and powder of the dry roots are snuffed in flue while the powder of the roots along with honey is given in cough and asthma.
76.	<i>Tamarixaphylla</i>	Tamaricaceae	Ghazz	Whole plant	Gum mixed with almonds is used to treat bone pain. The plant is also used as fuel, for shelter, and for making agricultural tools and furniture.
77	<i>Tuja orientalis</i>	Cupressaceae	Sarwa	Whole	Used for ornamental purposes.
78	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Markundy	Whole plant	Dried plants are used as fuel. Plant is used as fodder. Dried and grinded paste of fruits and leaves is used for aphrodisiacs, diabetes and fever. Fruit is used as diuretics and tonic.
79	<i>Verbscum Thapsus</i>	Scropohulariaceae	Khardag	Leaves and	Powdered leaves and flowers mixed with <i>Brassica</i> oil are

				flower	used as an antiseptic.
80	<i>Withiana somnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Kotilal	Fruit and leaves	The plant is used as liver tonic, anti-inflammatory, the dried plant also used as source of fuel.
81	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Asteraceae	Geshky	Leaves, roots and seed	Fruit is given in small doses (½-1 oz) as a tonic, cooling agent, and demulcent, and for chronic malaria and urinary diseases. The herb is also used in snakebite treatment.
82	<i>Zizyphus mauritiana</i>	Rhamnaceae	Markhanry	Fruit, leaves and branches	Fruit is edible and used as an astringent. wood used as fuel and fencing for and hedge. The leaves provide fresh fodder for goats. A honeybee species.
83	<i>Zizyphus nummularia</i>	Rhamnaceae	Karkanda	Fruits, leaves and branches.	Fruits are edible, young shoots are used as fodder. Used for burning purposes. It is used for constipation.
84	<i>Zizyphus jujube</i>	Rhamnaceae	Beera	Stem, Fruits, and Leaves.	Stem is used as shelter and fuel. Used for fencing. Leaves are used as food by animals. Fruits are eaten by local community. Plants are grown for hedge purposes. Fresh leaves are used for urinary infection and as blood purifier. It works as carminatives. Dried fruits powder is used as diabetes treatment. Fruits are also used for constipation.

Figure 1. Representation of Plant Species by Family in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda

Figure 2. Representation of Plant Species by used of plant parts in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda

Figure 3. Habit wise Representation of Plant Species in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda

Figure 4. Representation of Plant Species Used for Various Purposes in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda

Figure 5. Plants Used for the Treatment of Different Diseases in Tehsil Tangi, District Charsadda

Conclusion

Tehsil Tangi is rich in ethnobotanically important plants with significant medicinal, nutritional, and cultural uses. The local flora provides remedies for

gastrointestinal disorders, respiratory ailments, skin diseases, diabetes, and wound healing. Herbs dominate medicinal plant use, while trees and shrubs serve multifunctional roles as fodder, fuel, timber, and shelter. Indigenous knowledge plays a vital role

in traditional healthcare, especially where modern medical services are limited.

Author Contributions

Fazli Rahim designed and supervised the study and reviewed the manuscript. Shah Khalid collected ethnobotanical data and performed analysis. Anum Ali assisted in data collection and plant identification. Muhammad Atif ur Rehman and Mehreen Samad drafted and formatted the manuscript. Abid Ali assisted in fieldwork and manuscript revision. All authors approved the final manuscript.

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